

Investigation of the Specific Activity Concentration of ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th in Local Rice Produced in North-West Nigeria

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Abstract

Naturally Occurring Radioactive Material (NORM) present in food items constitutes a source of radiation hazard to man, it is therefore reasonable to evaluate the concentrations of these materials. In this study, twelve (12) rice samples were collected from different locations in north-west Nigeria, and two foreign rice species: Thailand and India were used to standardize the result. The rice samples were grinded, sealed in 100-mL plastic Marinelli beakers and the specific activity concentrations were measured in the laboratory. The counting time of 18 hours was used to monitor the gamma-ray spectra and the analysis of the specific activity of the radionuclides (^{40}K , ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th) was achieved with NaI (sodium iodide) detector. The specific activity of the radionuclide concentrations, (mean \pm error) in Bq/kg was obtained from the samples as (126.9028 \pm 6.8304), (32.2764 \pm 2.0549), (61.0267 \pm 5.5231), (24.3458 \pm 2.1199), (84.6744 \pm 6.2464) and (31.6719 \pm 1.3873) Bq/Kg for ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th respectively. ^{40}K percentage activity contribution show Thailand rice has the highest radionuclide contribution of 11% while Kura rice sample has the lowest contribution of 3% birnin kebbi and India rice sample contribute highest with 14% of the gross radium 226 and Warawa rice contribute with 3% concentrated more over riruwai doguwa and hadejia-jigawa contributed the highest percentage 12% to the total thorium activity while Kura rice is 3% concentrated which is less than the recommended limit of 370 Bq/kg by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. The total absorbed dose rate calculated from the activity concentration, ^{232}Th and ^{40}K ranges from 77 to 123 nGy h with an average value of 103 nGy h. The mean external (H_{ex}) and internal hazard indices (H_{in}) for the sample under study were determined to be 0.55 and 0.69, respectively. The corresponding average annual effective dose was found to be 0.63 mSv.

Keyword: Activity concentration, thorium nuclear analysis, potassium, Radium, Elemental concentration

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Introduction

Natural radio nuclides are pervasively prevalent in the environment, and even people carry radioactive substances inside of their bodies. Gamma radiation exposure caused by natural radioactivity has a geological and geographic dependence. These materials are present in various forms and concentrations. Regions in the world the primary sources of external

radiation on earth are the primordial isotopes of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , and ^{40}K , however there are large regional fluctuations in their quantities. (Hanfi, M.Y.L. et al.,2021) These radionuclides may be taken up by plant roots from the soil and transmitted to other areas of the plant, along with necessary nutrients. Human health problems are caused by radioactivity in crops' edible sections, exposure to intense ^{40}K is both

radiotoxic and a necessary nutrient, ^{226}Ra and ^{232}Th are radiotoxic elements (Mohammed Saad Alsaffar et al 2015). The existence of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM) in the Earth's crust is what causes natural radioactivity. The category of NORM radionuclides includes, among others, potassium-40 (^{40}K), uranium-238 (^{238}U and its decay series), and thorium 232 (^{232}Th and its decay series).

Together with the NORM, our environment is still home to a number of artificial radionuclides that were released owing to human activity in the late 1950s and early 1960s, such as plutonium-239+240 ($^{239+240}\text{Pu}$), cesium 137 (^{137}Cs), and strontium-90 (^{90}Sr). This man-made radionuclide has a long half-life. The half-lives $T(1/2)$ of ^{40}K , ^{238}U , ^{232}Th , $^{239}\text{Pu}/^{240}\text{Pu}$, ^{137}Cs , and ^{90}Sr are, respectively, 1.3E9a, 4.5E9a, 1.4E10, 24E3/6.56E3a, and 28; today, these radionuclides are typically present in air, soil and water in varying degrees (Tran Thi Van et al: 2008; Kolbel, L et al, 2020).

According to the kind of soil, its chemical properties, the physics and chemical forms of the radionuclides in the soil, radionuclide absorption by certain plants, and finally the level accumulated by specific foodstuffs, the release of radionuclides into the environment contaminates food (Abdalsattar Hashim, Laith A. Najam 2015; Gaafar.L.M.et al.,2018; Raswan, M.A et al.,2019). It is well known that foods contain both man-made and natural radionuclides, which when consumed, contribute to an efficient internal dosage. The main source of man's exposure to naturally occurring radiation is from radionuclides, particularly those of the ^{238}U and 232nd series and ^{40}K . According to estimates, consuming food accounts for at least one-eighth of the mean annual effective dosage from natural sources (T.Hossein et all : 2006 Laith A Najam al.2005;

Gaafar L.M. Abdrabbor et al.2018; Rashwan et al.,2019). The first step to achieve these goal is to measure background gamma radiation level of region. Results of this measurement can also be used as a reference value to evaluate effects of manmade radiation. A thorough literature search reveals a small number of studies on the radionuclide content of food consumed in Kuwait(Al-Azmi et al.1999;Alrefae,2012;Alrefae et al.2012).such scarcity was the main motive to conduct the current study, in order to meet the important national requirement of establishing a baseline of radioactivity exposure to the general public from food consumption a systematic approach, this study focused on one type of foodstuff that is widely consumed by various age group in Nigeria, namely rice.

The purpose of this research was to measure the amount of long-lasting gamma emitting substances in rice consumed in northwestern state region Nigeria. Additionally, the study aimed to calculate annual effective doses that the general public receives from consuming this rice. It is important to investigate the radioactivity of rice that people eat in order to determine the potential health risk associated with it. ^{226}Ra is an α -emitter with long half-life of 1600y is of particular concern as it is closely mimics the behavior of calcium in the human body and can accumulate in bones over time, leading to potential health problem and radio-toxicity due to prolong exposure. Thus, since the study on the investigation of long live gamma emitter in locally process rice from northwestern state of Nigeria and estimate of annual effective dose have not been reported, radionuclide content in locally processed rice from northwestern state will be investigated in this study.

Conceptual Framework

The level of Environmental natural radiation is significantly influenced by the geological and geographical characteristics of a region, as well as the building material utilized in that region. Hence the background radiation level can vary across different geographical location highly depends on (Ali mahmoud pashazadeh et al: 2014; Mashaly, A. O. et al 2016). Human-made radioactive elements generated by human activities add to environmental activity. One of the significant human-made radioactive elements that concern the environment is Cs. To evaluate the level contamination in the food consumed by the public, it is crucial to determine the baseline value of radiation level from both natural and Human made radio active element they are exposed to (T. Hosseini et al:2006; Cumber Land S. A. et al 2016; Moussa H.E. 2021; Rashwan, M. A. et al 2019). The presence of radioactivity in the environment can be attributed to two sources: natural and anthropogenic (man-made) sources. Radionuclides include isotopes of potassium (^{40}K), uranium (^{238}U and its decay series), and thorium (^{232}Th), and its decay series). these natural occurring radioactive materials (NORM) have a long half-life (approximately of 1010 year) and can commonly be found in environmental samples. Both natural and anthropogenic radionuclides are present in the food chain of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystem and eventually accumulate in the human body through food consumption. As a result, Global attention is focused on the level of radiation exposure experienced by human due to the intake of radionuclide from food. Rice is widely consumed food type globally

Therefore, research on the radioactivity levels in rice has been conducted in various regions worldwide since 1999. The findings of these studies have been essentials in establishing a baseline for radiation exposure resulting from rice consumption (Tareq Alrefae, Tiruvachi N. Nageswaran, 2012).

Gamma radiation has always been existed in environment since the big bang occurred. During the last few decades radioisotopes and nuclear explosions in upper layers of the atmosphere contaminated and polluted the earth badly. the radioactive nuclides, produced due to those explosions, contaminated the entire environment. At surface layers of soil, these radioactive elements have higher level of concentration because their migration to down to the earth is limited. Foodstuff are known to contain natural and man-made radionuclides which after ingestion, contribute to an effective internal dose. the naturally occurring radionuclides especially ^{40}K and the radionuclides of ^{238}U and ^{232}Th series are the major source of natural radiation exposure to the man.it has been estimated that at least one-eighth of the mean annual effective dose due to natural sources is caused by the consumption of foodstuff (laith A. Najam et.al 2015). The assessment of the radiation level and its impact on the environment has received great attention worldwide. This is because of the negative health effects ionizing radiation has on biological tissues, when highly energetic ionizing radiation interacts with biological tissues, it causes ionization with subsequent release of charged particle and free radicals thereby causing alteration in cell structure and damage to deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA). A damage to the DNA result in gene mutation, chromosomal aberration and breakages or cell death. Some of the health effects of long term exposure to radiation and the inhalation/ingestion of radionuclides are chronic lung disease, acute leucopenia, anemia necrosis of the mouth, cataract, chronic lung cancer and leukemia. cancer still remains one major harmful effects produced by ionizing radiation (Fredrick O. Ugedede, Eugene O. Echeweozo 2017).

Food is known to contain natural and artificial radionuclides that, after ingestion, contribute to an effective internal dose.it has been estimated

that a large portion, at least one eighth, of the mean annual dose due to natural sources is caused by the intake of food. Average radiation doses to various organs of the body also represents important pathway for long term health considerations (Rafat M. Amin and Fawzia Ahmed 2013).

Materials and Methods

Sample collection and preparation

A total of 12 rice species was collected from the sampled region. A sample was collected from each area, the sample were clean 12 sample of locally process rise samples were collected from the local market in the respective northwestern state. The collection took place between April and May of 2021.to ensure a comprehensive and a wide-spread representation, each sample were made to become a powdered and placed in a Marinelli beaker. After being sealed, the sample-filled containers were left for a period of at least 4-6 weeks to reach secular equilibrium between parent radio nuclides and their daughters.

Gamma ray measurement

Measurements were performed using gamma ray spectrometer detector in which the gamma line will indicate the presence of radionuclides in the measured sample (Alrefea et al 2012; Arumma et al 2021). The gamma-ray spectrum analysis of the rice sample for natural radioactivity will be carried out by gamma spectrometer.

Radiation Activity

The activity concentration of ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K will be calculated using the following relation (Civa Kumar et al 2020)

$$A = \frac{C_o}{\epsilon P_r M_s} \text{----- (1)}$$

Where A: activity concentration in (Bq/kg)
 C_o: net counting rate of gamma ray (count per second) ε detector efficiency of the specific gamma ray P_r Absolute transition probability of gamma decay M_s mass of the sample in (kg)for ²³⁸U, ²³²Th, and its radioactive decay progenies,

as well as ¹³⁷Cs and ⁴⁰K in rice can be evaluated using the following expression (UN SCEAR 2015: Foreshore al,2018)

$$Ra_{eq} = A_{Ra} + 1.43A_{Th} + 0.77A_k \text{ (2)}$$

Where A_{Ra} is activity of Ra A_{Th} is the activity of Th A_k is the activity of K, the concentration or exposure to radiation resulting from gamma rays which is used to calculate risk of concentration was calculated using the equation (2) above. Internal and external risk were also calculated

$$H_{ex} = \frac{A_{Ra}}{370} \frac{A_{Th}}{259} + \frac{A_k}{4810} \leq 1 \text{ (3)}$$

$$H_{ex} = \frac{A_{Ra}}{185} \frac{A_{Th}}{259} + \frac{A_k}{4810} \leq 1. \text{ (4)}$$

As a result of the food intake, the annual effective dose was also calculated the metabolic developed by was supported by ICRP17 as

$$Eff = \sum(A.C_r) * R_f \text{ (5)}$$

Discussion

This preliminary assessment of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM) content in Rice samples within the area of study has indicated a slight rise in activity levels though within the acceptable limit for the general public. The Samples in this study area therefore considered to be safe radiological for human consumption.

The results of the radionuclide analysis carried out on the twelve Rice produces are presented in Figure 1, the result of the 40K activity concentration presented in Figure 2 shows a value range of 40.5962 ± 2.0200 Bq/Kg in Kura Rice Sample to 166.6993 ± 9.6098 Bq/Kg in Thailand Rice Sample with a mean value of 126.9028 ± 6.8304 q/Kg and Standard Deviation Value of 32.2764 ± 2.0549. The activity concentration of Radium – 226 ranged from 24.4009 ± 2.7762 Bq/Kg in Warawa Rice Sample to 104.3250 ± 8.6207 Bq/Kg in India Rice sample with a mean value of 61.0267 ± 5.5231 Bq/Kg and Standard Deviation Value of

24.3458 \pm 2.1199. While the activity concentration in Thorium – 232 ranged from 33.06207 \pm 6.8966 Bq/Kg in Kura Rice Sample to 121.2643 \pm 6.6667 Bq/Kg in Riruwai Doguwa Rice Sample with a mean value of 84.6744 \pm 6.2464 Bq/Kg and Standard Deviation Value of 31.6719 \pm 1.3873.

Table 1. The result of radioactivity analysis Weight of container + sample

S/N	SAMPLE ID	SAMPLE CODE	Weight of empty container	Weight of container +sample	Weight of sample	Date sealed
1	kano	AI	36.00g	192.22g	156.22g	21-04.-2021
2	Sumaila	A2	28.14g	197.89g	169.75g	21-04.-2021
3	Thailand	A3	32.78g	189.43g	156.65g	21-04.-2021
4	Warawa	A4	33.28g	162.36g	129.08g	21-04.-2021
5	Tudun wada	A5	33.75g	203.12g	169.84g	21-04.-2021
6	ririwai-dogowa	A6	38.02g	211.32g	173.3g	21-04.-2021
7	funtuwa- katsina	A7	31.08g	196.62g	165.54g	21-04.-2021
8	hadejia-jigwa	A8	29.29g	208.28g	178.99g	21-04.-2021
9	gusau zamfara	A9	32.58g	212.68g	180.1g	21-04.-2021
10	zaria kaduna	A10	33.11g	198.21g	165.1g	21-04.-2021
11	birnin kebbi- kebbi	A11	30.48g	200.62g	174.14g	21-04.-2021
12	india	A	29.52g	204.42g	174.90g	21-04.-2021

Table 2. The values of Ra, Th and 40k activity content using gamma ray spectrometry and Ra activity in rice samples

S/N	Sample Location	Sample ID	K-40 (Bq/kg)	Error = (Bq/Kg)	Ra-226 (Bq/kg)	Error = (Bq/Kg)	Th-232 (Bq/kg)	Error = (Bq/Kg)
1	kano	AI	40.5962	2.02	41.204	5.5523	33.621	6.8966
2	sumaila	A2	144.734	6.4719	34.4828	2.1917	49.425	5.8908
3	Thailand	A3	166.699	9.6098	51.4319	4.0912	62.5	3.5919
4	warawa	A4	104.51	7.2549	24.4009	2.7762	41.37	4.454
5	Tudun Wada	A5	143.33	7.4509	56.0537	3.2145	99.425	6.5086
6	ririwai-dogowa	A6	135.098	5.7863	67.694	5.5669	121.26	6.6667
7	funtuwa- katsina	A7	109.508	6.2765	85.4763	7.5979	109.48	8.4914
8	hadejia-jigwa	A8	137.647	7.4706	50.5475	3.0684	118.1	5.7471
9	gusau zamfara	A9	127.245	7.1765	72.7645	6.0491	99.713	6.6236
10	zaria kaduna	A10	105.686	4.31314	43.834	4.09121	104.9	8.0459
11	birnin kebbi- kebbi	A11	149.508	8.8235	99.7954	7.8901	69.397	4.7414

12	india	A	158..0588	9.4118	104.325	8.6207	106.9	7.2989
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Figure 1: Activity concentration in the Rice Sample

Figure 2: Percentage Activity concentration of 40-K in the Rice Sample

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Conclusion

The current study showed the presence of significant Radioactivity in the twelve samples of Rice consumed within the area of study was determined using the gamma ray spectrometry. The research has revealed that there is a rise in the level of naturally occurring radioactive in some Rice samples.

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Conflict of Interest

The author has no conflict of Interest

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